

Sm@RT

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Technologies on sheep & goat farms

A European network to share experiences of new technologies for sheep and goats.

An online survey, carried out during Spring 2021, was designed to collect information from stakeholders involved in the small ruminant meat and dairy industries across Europe & Israel.

Data collected allowed the assessment of current needs and barriers of technology implementation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, under grant agreement 101000471.

Who are involved in Sm@RT?

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

8 Countries

Estonia
France
Hungary
Ireland
Italy
Israel
Norway
United Kingdom

More than 650
survey respondents

452 farmers/shepherds
121 consultants/advisors
85 veterinarians
12 others

The 85 UK respondents
were from all around
the country

63 farmers/shepherds
15 consultants/advisors
7 veterinarians

Meat sheep	Farm area (ha)	Number of sheep
UK	Average: 336ha (2-4,500ha)	Average: 471 ewes (8-3,400 ewes)
All countries	Average: 319ha (0.15-30,000ha)	Average: 340 ewes (4-3,400 ewes)

Methodology

Respondents were asked to:

- Select the **technologies they have** on their farm
- Select which **technologies they would like** to use on their farm
- Rank the **5 technologies they deemed most beneficial** to their system

Technologies currently on farm

All productions

Meat sheep

Top 3 technologies currently on all farms:

1. Weigh crate
2. Farm / herd management software
3. Camera / Video Camera

"I have the technology because it is relevant to my system."

"The technology is convenient for collecting information about my flock."

Top 3 technologies currently on UK farms:

1. Weigh crate
2. Farm / herd management software
3. Camera / Video Camera

Technologies farmers would like to have

All productions

Meat sheep

Top 3 technologies that farmers would like very much:

1. Weigh crate
2. EID stick reader
3. EID autodrafter

"My neighbour has this technology and they have found it very helpful."

"I think this technology is too expensive and complicated."

Top 3 technologies that UK farmers would like very much:

1. Weigh crate
2. Camera / Video Camera
3. EID worming gun

Top 5 technologies deemed most beneficial

All productions

Meat sheep

Top 3 technologies that farmers deemed most beneficial (selected as top 1):

1. Weigh crate
2. Virtual Fences
3. Flock / herd management software

"Using a weigh crate allows me to monitor how my lambs are growing."

"It would be beneficial to have all of the data I have on my flock, and farm, in one place."

Top 3 technologies that UK farmers deemed most beneficial (selected as top 1):

1. Weigh crate
2. Virtual Fences
3. Flock / herd management software

www.smartplatform.network

linktr.ee/h2020smart

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, under grant agreement 101000471.